

Knowledge Point		Patient Inquiry		
Description		A 50-year-old male patient comes to the clinic of the Department of Orthopedics. Please take the patient's medical history.		
Items	Score	Scoring Standards	Sub-items	Final Score
Preparation	4	Say hello to the patient and introduce yourself	2	
		Be friendly, sincere, enthusiastic and articulate	2	
General information	3	Name, gender and age (1 point per item)	3	
Chief complaint	10	The left foot suffered swelling and effusion for half a month	10	
History of present illness	58	1. Onset: acute/chronic; sudden/gradual; onset time (1 point per item)	5	
		2. Cause: diabetes, trauma (2 points per item)	4	
		3. Main symptoms: delayed healing of foot, the duration; relieving factors; aggravating factors; whether it is complicated by lower limb chills, difficulty in walking, intermittent claudication, or rest pain (3 points per item)	24	
		4. Development and evolution of the disease: aggravated; alleviated (2 points per item)	4	
		5. Accompanying symptoms: pain, numbness, decreased skin temperature, gangrene, etc. (1 point per item)	7	
		6. Diagnosis and treatment: whether the patient sought medical treatment in other hospitals (2 points per item)	2	
		7. General conditions: diet, sleep, mental health, urine and feces, physical strength, and weight (2 points per item)	12	
Past medical history	4	Previous health status: whether the patient had any diseases or any chronic diseases like hypertension and diabetes (2 points per item)	4	
Personal history	4	Addiction: alcohol and tobacco (2 points per item)	4	
Family history	3	Health status of spouse, children and parents (1 point per item)	3	
Communication	2	Discuss with the patient on the results, the examination required and the opinions for initial treatment	2	
Inquiry skills	12	1. Ask well-organized questions	2	
		2. Do not ask any leading or challenging question. Do not keep asking questions	2	

		without pause. One point will be deducted for each of the violations above until all points are deducted		
		3. Do not ask questions with medical terms. If they are used, explain to the patient immediately	2	
		4. The questioner should listen to the patient carefully. Do not interrupt rudely	2	
		5. Be courteous and respectful to the patient through friendly eye contact, sympathy and encouraging words	2	
		6. Thank the patient for his cooperation at the end of inquiry	2	
Total	100		100	

Knowledge Point		Physical Examination		
Description		A 50-year-old male patient comes to the clinic of the Department of Orthopedics. Please perform a detailed physical examination of the patient before admission.		
Items	Score	Scoring Standards	Sub-items	Final Score
Preparation	10	Doctor's preparation: wear work clothes, mask and hat; wash hands; use cotton swabs and gloves (or by oral expression)	2	
		Check the patient's information	2	
		Communicate with the patient: introduce the test to be performed and gain support	2	
		Position of the patient: the patient is in supine position with extensive exposure on both sides	2	
		Position of the examiner: the examiner stands on the patient's right side	2	
Visual examination	20	Examination in supine position: whether the affected limb is deformed or atrophic	5	
		Swelling of affected limb: whether there is hyperemia or redness	5	
		Local skin color (2 points), sinus tract/scar (2 points), pigmentation (2 points), varicose veins (2 points), and lump (2 points)	10	
Palpation and percussion	20	Local skin temperature, local tenderness	10	
		Whether there is any palpable enclosed mass (describe its property if yes)	10	
Motility measurement	30	Ask the patient to move the foot. Observe the range of motion (flexion and extension, adduction and abduction, inward and outward rotation). Compare the motion on both sides	10	
		Move the patient's ankle joint (flexion and extension, adduction and abduction, inward and outward rotation). Observe the range of motion. Compare the motion on both sides	10	
		Measure muscle strength in all directions of the ankle joint (abduction, adduction, forward bend, backward stretch)	10	
Basic principles	15	Whether the motion is compared on both sides with extensive exposure	2	
		Whether the patient is asked to move the foot before the doctor moves the foot	3	
		Whether the examination follows the right order (1. Observe the affected part; 2. Touch the affected part; 3. Check the range of motion; 4. Measure the length)	5	
		Whether the physical examination is performed	5	

		in a comprehensive and reasonable way		
Overall evaluation	5	Whether the examination is performed expertly with correct methods and compassionate care	5	
Total	100		100	

Knowledge Point		Write Medical Records		
Items	Score	Scoring Standards	Sub-items	Final Score
Chief complaint	15	The comprehensive and concise information can reflect the disease's characteristics and help generate the first diagnosis	15	
		The information is basically accurate and can help generate the first diagnosis	10	
		The chief complaint is complicated, but it can still help generate the first diagnosis	5	
		The information cannot help generate the first diagnosis	0	
History of present illness	30	The patient's condition from onset to diagnosis, main symptoms, evolution, accompanying symptoms, development of the disease and general conditions are all recorded on basis of chief complaint	30	
		The description of medical history is basically complete but puts less emphasis on key points	20	
		The description of medical history is complete. Some items including cause of disease, main symptoms, accompanying symptoms, progression of disease, diagnosis and treatment are omitted, but the omission doesn't affect the diagnosis	10	
		The description of medical history has material omissions. Some items including cause of disease, main symptoms, accompanying symptoms, warning of disease, diagnosis and treatment are omitted or incorrectly recorded. The omission or incorrect record affect the diagnosis	0	
Past medical history, personal history, allergic history, marital and reproductive history, family history	5	The medical history is detailed and complete	5	
		The medical history is less detailed and complete	2.5	
		The medical history has material omissions	0	
Physical examination	10	The medical history is recorded in the right order	10	
		The medical history is basically recorded in the right order	5	
		The medical history is disorderly and unsystematic	0	
		The diagnosis has a complete but insufficient basis	7	
		The diagnosis does not have a complete basis	3	
		The diagnosis has no basis	0	
Diagnosis on admission	10	The diagnosis is accurate, comprehensive, standard and complete	10	
		The diagnosis is basically standard, comprehensive and accurate	5	
		The diagnosis is incorrect	0	
Treatment measures	10	The measures are accurate and complete	10	
		The measures are basically accurate and complete	5	
		The measures have some errors of principle	0	
Write medical	10	The writing is standardized, neat and orderly	10	

records		without any sign of erasure and wrongly written or mispronounced characters		
		The writing is basically standardized, but has some sign of erasure and wrongly written or mispronounced characters	7	
		The writing is not standardized, and has many signs of erasure and wrongly written or mispronounced characters	3	
Total	100		100	

Knowledge Point		Read X-rays		
Description		A 50-year-old male patient comes to the clinic of the Department of Orthopedics. Please read the patient's X-rays.		
Items	Score	Scoring Standards	Sub-items	Final Score
Skim through the X-rays	10	The X-rays are clearly displayed and properly exposed. Bone tissue is easily distinguishable from soft tissue	10	
Distinguish the radiographs accurately	20	Left and right sides	10	
		Foot AP & LAT, ankle AP & LAT	10	
Distinguish soft tissue from bone tissue	20	Whether the soft tissue is swollen and has a shadow of subcutaneous pneumatosis. Identify the location and range of swellings	20	
	20	Whether the bone cortex is continuous and intact and the sclerotin is damaged. Identify the location and range of damaged sclerotin	20	
Whether the extent of the damage to bone and soft tissue displayed in X-rays matches the results of physical examination. If not matched, identify the reasons: 1. Unable to read the manifestation of soft tissue shadow in X-rays. 2. Diabetic foot usually results from the decreased ability to resist infection when the ischemia in soft tissues causes inadequate perfusion. The bone tissue is seldom damaged. B-scan of left lower extremity: vein occlusion or massive plaque formation			30	
Total	100		100	

Knowledge Point		Case Analysis		
Description		A 50-year-old male patient comes to the clinic of the Department of Orthopedics. Please take the patient's medical history.		
Items	Score	Scoring Standards	Sub-items	Final Score
Chief complaint	20	The left foot suffered swelling and effusion for half a month	20	
History of present illness	20	The 50-year-old patient reported that the medial side of the first toe of the left foot was accidentally scratched 1 month ago. Given a small amount of bleeding, he sterilized and bandaged the wound, but the wound never healed. As the redness, swelling and effusion were aggravated, he took antibiotics orally (lack of details) but the effect was unsatisfactory. Therefore, he came to our hospital for further diagnosis and treatment.	20	
Physical examination	10	Physical examination: check the foot The first toe of the left foot and the medial side of the forefoot had obvious swelling and a relatively low skin temperature. A 2x3cm wound was seen on the medial side of the first toe. The wound had a white edge and exuded sticky yellow liquid, but did not reach the sclerotin. The active/passive flexion and extension of interphalangeal joints and metatarsophalangeal joints of the left foot were restricted and significantly weakened.	10	
Family history	5	Left foot AP & LAT: No obvious sclerotin damage was observed in the left foot. The soft tissue swelled at the first metatarsophalangeal joints of the left foot.	5	
	5	B-scan of veins in the left lower extremity: multiple plaques were formed in the veins of the left lower extremity	5	
History of diabetes	10	The patient was diagnosed with type 2 diabetes at a local hospital 15 years ago, but did not take it seriously. He did not use hypoglycemic drugs and test blood glucose on a regular basis. The random blood glucose on admission was 16 mmol/L.	10	
Diagnosis	20	The patient had a history of diabetes and was infected	10	
		Type 2 diabetes	10	
Treatment	10	Test and control the blood glucose level	5	
		Debride the wound of the left foot, drain the fluid continuously, and suture the wound in the next phase	5	
Total	100		100	